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DESIGNING URBAN SOUNDSCAPES - DEFINING CULTURAL LANDSCAPES

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ABSTRACT

Soundscapes, or acoustic environments, are part of natural, multi-sensory territorial experiences. The symbolic properties of sounds can influence perceptions of landscapes. In spite of this, the analysis and design of auditory experiences are rarely undertaken, resulting in territorial sound elements which are mere byproducts of everyday human activity. The discipline of acoustic design aims to enable the deliberate composition of environmental sound, thus contributing to shaping the subject's interpretation of his environment. This study aims to identify the key aspects of urban soundscapes which influence territorial interpretation. Acoustic design methodology, as originally conceived by R. Murray Schafer, is revisited through the lens of interpretative anthropology, communication theory and design. The aesthetic and social dimensions of the soundscape are considered and, additionally, a soundwalk methodology is presented as a model for the analysis of urban soundscapes. This study concludes with reflections on the application of soundwalk methodology.

Keywords: Acoustic Ecology, Soundscapes, Design.

INTRODUCTION

Although territorial experiences are fundamentally multi-sensory, relatively few studies have emerged addressing the auditory dimension of those experiences. Like other sensory phenomena, sounds inform us as to the nature of objective reality. This is evident when one considers, for example, the sounds which frame the city, the densely populated territories which have become the locus of cultural

and economic production. The industrial sounds heard within the city define those places to the degree that, in sound alone, an urban environment can be identified.

Fields which aim to shape territorial experiences through design - architecture, experience and service design, to name a few - stand to gain in addressing the full range of human senses. This study focuses on the design of sound experiences, with a specific emphasis on the soundwalk method for the investigation of territorial sound. Sound is approached from an interpretive standpoint: the meanings which emerge from the interpretation of sound phenomena are an important product of the method contained herein.

The theoretical foundations for the analysis of territory through sound rely primarily on the work of authors from the field of sound studies, whose investigations involve topics such as acoustic ecology, acoustic design, acoustemology and acoustic communication. The reflections herein contained on sound methodology for territorial design are particularly relevant to the discipline of strategic design, with an approach which integrates product and service offerings, concentrating on the elements of user centered experience, communication, sustainability and social needs (MERONI, 2008). In fact, components of communication and experience make up a significant part of both strategic design and sound studies. There is an aim within the field of sound studies to broach the perceptual and interpretive nature of sound reception, and extensive approaches have been developed to examine auditory experience. Many other areas have also advanced in this endeavor - psychology, anthropology, music and design, for example (FELD, 2004; NORMAN, 2004;

IHDE, 2007). The scope of this article is to introduce significant theory for the study of auditory environments, which can lead to methods for empirical research. There is, therefore, a deliberate focus on offering tools to designers who wish to incorporate sound analysis techniques into their problem setting and solving process.

DESIGNING SOUND

Although the term sound design has been widely used to designate the design of sound for visual media such as video and film, it is obvious that the field predates electric media. If design can be defined as the human capacity to shape objects in meaningful ways to serve our needs (HESKETT, 2005), then sound can be, and has been, manipulated in this same way throughout history. The symbolic dimension of church bells and judge gavels have important social functions. One could point to similar functions in music and the spoken word.

The field of sound design has been broadened to address the auditory dimension human-object interaction. For example, recently, the European Cooperation in Science and Technology has promoted research in sonic interaction design, which constitutes an "inquiry into any of various roles that sound may play in the interaction loop between users and artifacts, services, or environments" (ROCCHESSO, SERAFIN, et al., 2008, p.3969). Similarly, during the early 1990's, the fields of auditory display and sonification were developed to address the need for a formal study of how sound elements can represent data (HERMANN, 2008). Auditory display is a research field which addresses the function of sound in communicating computer data, while sonification is the actual data-to-audio rendering process.

The following section describes some basic concepts related to the discipline of soundscape studies, which has existed in some form since the 1960s, and which offers appropriate theory for the study of territorial sound.

SOUND STUDIES THEORY

The sound studies have been approached from perspectives such as phenomenology, anthropology, environmental health, aesthetics, communication

theory and design. And although the literature of this area widely acknowledges that sight still constitutes the primary mode of perception in society (BULL, 2002; SCHAFER, 1977), it is also obvious that the auditory dimension of experience is fundamental to communication and culture. The spoken word, environmental sounds and music are but three essential elements of everyday life. Additionally, there is the desire among theorists to develop knowledge in alignment with a "democracy of the senses" (BULL e BLACK, 2003, p. 2), through which more attention to sound as a component of experience may be afforded.

The ecological nature of sound becomes a recurring topic in sounds studies. Indeed, acoustic ecology - the relationship of acoustic environments and humans- is of significant relevance to the study of territory and sound (SCHAFER, 1977).

Acoustics is perhaps a better known field for the study of sound and territory, especially as it relates to architecture. Yet the typical approach taken in acoustics defines sounds as either auditory stimulus or sensation, both in a biological sense (EVEREST, 2001). For this reason, this study relies on an epistemological approach which originates in the social sciences, which affords a relevant examination of the symbolic dimension of soundscapes.

Sound studies allows for an exploration of cultural and subjective experience, and is especially relevant for examining urban space. The persistent aural backdrop of the city becomes its own inherent interpretive quality - "sound gives us the city as matter and as memory" (TONKISS, 2003, p. 303). This "sonic environment" is known as a soundscape (SCHAFER, 1977, p. 274). Soundscapes can be examined in terms of their three constitutive aural elements: keynote sounds, sound signals and soundmarks.

Keynote sounds are those that are perceived as habitual over time. The constancy of keynote sounds reduces awareness of their occurrence - for example, sounds of traffic can cease to be noticed in detail by city dwellers (Ibid.). Because of the diminished attention allocated to these sounds, they are perceived in an activity called background listening (TRUAX, 2001). Keynote sounds contribute significantly to the sonic identity of territories, potentially influencing human behavior and

reflecting the fundamental characteristics of an environment (Ibid.).

The reduced conscious perception of keynote sounds is partially due to their repetitive, unchanging character. Truax mentions air conditioners as examples of these keynotes, pointing to their constant intensity levels, as well as their broad frequency content (Ibid.). Similarly, in nature, an equivalent auditory phenomenon is the constancy of ocean sounds, which would potentially comprise a keynote sound in the perceptions of a nearby community.

Sound signals are sounds which stand out from the keynote background. They occur intermittently and demand attention: examples include church bells and car horns. When these sounds convey information about a unique territorial context, that is, when they are identified as the native sounds of a specific place, the signal is called a soundmark.

Soundmarks carry amplified symbolism, contributing to an expanded interpretation of the environment. The aforementioned church bells could exemplify a soundmark, providing a receiver is capable of identifying the particular bells as from a specific territory. Car horns, on the other hand, produce sounds which are shared by other cars of a same type, and which exist in different places. Thus they are sound signals, as they cannot be interpreted as territorial differentiators.

The use of the sound signal, soundmark and keynote sound concepts is instrumental in the analysis and design of soundscapes, as is developing the ability to perceive these elements. Authors also suggest clear objectives to orient these studies. According to Truax, this can be “to define the environmental characteristics that promote effective communication within any environment under study” (Ibid, p. 62). Likewise, Schafer describes an ideal situation where the design of soundscapes gives priority to enhancing desirable sounds, as opposed to focusing on the abatement of unwanted sources. It is conceivable that the obstruction of interfering sound from soundscape designs may be impossible. This may be why the aforementioned authors tend to focus on the improvement of desirable sound, which can be manipulated and shaped more easily. The alternative would be, simply, noise abatement.

Noise abatement is, of course, also an option when designing soundscapes. Careful territorial planning - perhaps using natural barriers - can attenuate intruding noise. Hedfors describes “auditory refuges”, where “listeners perceive themselves to be in control of their acoustic environment” (HEDFORS, 2003, p. 60).

After a preliminary examination of the acoustic environment, the designer of soundscapes can manipulate sound to facilitate a more meaningful experience by the receiver. Based on the effects the designer wishes to produce, sound can be used, for example, to inform, persuade, entertain and stir emotions. Which criteria should be used to navigate the possibilities in soundscape design? Following is a description of possible criteria, based in part on previous work related to positive soundscapes (Adams et al.).

POSITIVE VS. NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF SOUND

Many authors have conceptualized “better” or “worse” sound with regard to territory. Norman describes negative and positive affect in his study of the emotional responses to specific sounds, using the design of an industrial plant as an example. He describes “buzzing, ringing alarms” as “negative and anxiety producing” (NORMAN, 2004, p. 28). Moreover, the author points to the threat of excessive negative stimuli, which may result in the subject’s failure to focus on important information. Positive auditory stimuli can take several forms. Norman states that “natural sounds are the best conveyors of meaning” (Ibid, p. 120), while Schafer describes, in relation to noise abatement campaigns, a social disapproval of the noise produced by “reckless technology” (SCHAFER, 1977, p. 87). Bijsterveld points out that the attitude of some social groups toward technological sound is that of “deliberate disruption” - noise -, “often by those lower in the [social] hierarchy” (BIJSTERVELD, 2003, p. 60). Nonetheless, it cannot be implied that sounds whose sources are technological, or urban, are always perceived as negative. “Loud sounds, if positively evaluated, have been attributed with characteristics such as power, strength, progress, prosperity, energy, dynamics, masculinity and control” (Ibid, p. 182). The loud roar of the motorcycle engine evokes positive emotions from

many Harley Davidson enthusiasts (LYON, 2003). These different positions reflect the ambiguities, symbolic properties and cultural contexts related to sound, and by extension, the respective soundscapes.

As illustrated above, it is possible to interpret industrial and economic development through sound, just as social stratification can be reinforced through the interpretation of the sound-producing symbolic behavior of specific groups. Response to sound -- be it to sonic attributes of intensity or character -- can depend, therefore, on "situation of use, expectation and other factors" (Ibid., p. 19).

Investigating and influencing soundscapes should entail a search for an aesthetically acceptable and a socially constructive auditory experience -- positive sound. Cain et al. describe positive soundscapes as "activity centric", based on receiver context, and not primarily related to the formal characteristics of the sounds themselves. The views of other authors corroborate the importance of the symbolic dimension of sound, with theory that examines how receivers constitute their attitudes toward sound and territory through the practice of listening and interpreting (FELD, 2004; SCHAFER, 1977; TRUAX, 2001).

A central theme in the discipline of acoustic ecology is the importance of developing a socially responsible practice, taking into account the ecological effects of soundscapes (SCHAFER, 1977). Victor Papanek asserts that design, which should be culturally relevant and inclusive, has "great moral and social responsibilities" (PAPANEK, 2009, p. 72). The design of sound should share such sensibilities. Therefore, in the context of the territorial design activities presented in this article, and broadly based on the theory of sound studies and design, this article posits positive sound as being both culturally relevant and inclusive.

Culturally relevant territorial sound should be clearly understood by receivers and must take into account their social contexts -- Schafer states a principle of acoustic design as "an awareness of sound symbolism" (SCHAFER, 1977, p. 238). Designed sound should also be socially inclusive, taking into account the needs and desires of all groups who inhabit the respective territories. An emphasis should be given to those groups especially affected by sound -- those with

sensory impairments as well as those who will occupy the territory for prolonged periods. Addressing auditory impairment may require that the designer pay special attention to sound intensity, and designing for visual impairment may require more attention to the appropriateness of auditory content, so as to better orient within surrounding environments.

In what follows, the soundwalk method is presented as an approach to the study of soundscapes, allowing designers to interact and observe territories by means of sound.

A METHOD OF SOUNDSCAPE INVESTIGATION: THE SOUNDWALK

Qualitative research methods can help to shed light on the nature of sound reception in urban contexts, as well as the sonic dimension of the social construction of public space. The current corpus of sound research methodology still lacks a deliberate focus on offering tools to designers who wish to incorporate immersive listening activities into a more traditional problem setting and solving process. Fortunately, the field of sound studies offers a starting point for these activities in the soundwalk method.

Schafer asserts the importance of field work in the study of soundscapes, which, as "living environments", provide information about meaningful sound (SCHAFER, 1977, p. 12). The author proposes the discipline of soundscape studies, which uses the soundwalk method as an "exploration of the soundscape of a given area". Westercamp describes the soundwalks as "any excursion whose main purpose is listening to the environment" (WESTERKAMP, 1974). In this way, soundwalks shift the primary mode of observation from the visual to auditory.

These listening activities usually take the form of guided walks which aim to observe the sound phenomena in specific territories, giving "our ears priority" (Ibid). Much like anthropological field studies, soundwalks provide information from the researcher's direct, immersive experience. The method can also be applied with a group of participating subjects, who take the walk together, aided by a facilitator. The group can discuss the soundscape during or after the activity (always when

signaled by the facilitator), and individually through subsequent interviewing.

Soundwalking is different from passively listening to environments: practitioners must engage the soundscape, observing the aforementioned signals, soundmarks and keynotes (SCHAFER, 1977). The soundwalk method can be a valuable instrument for the study of the interpretation of territorial sound, as participants focus their attention on what would otherwise be a sonic backdrop, and listening shifts from passive to active.

Soundwalks can make use of a guide, or “map”, to orient the reception process. Maps can be useful for documenting, organizing and repeating routes and activities. Some authors have presented variations to the soundwalk method which forego the use of formal maps and diminish the degree of interaction between the researcher and the environment.

The soundwalk method presented here uses maps, prescribes field documentation, and results in data for an analysis of the soundscape. This final step takes the form of an ecological and ethnographic analysis in the form of descriptive text.

A guide should be present for the soundwalk, and there is no upper limit for the number of participants. However, one should be careful with distractions associated with the organized movement of participants between locations. Should be soundwalk be conducted with participants other than the designers, the selection of these participants should take demographic criteria into account - relevant to the population of end-users for the territory being studied. They should also wear comfortable clothing and carry as little as possible, save for note taking equipment.

Before beginning a soundwalk, the guide should inform participants of the route that will be taken, the expected duration and a set of rules of conduct which ensure the best possible auditory observation. Following, three further soundwalk elements are proposed.

CONSTITUTION AND USE OF A MAP

The use of a map allows for a guided toward an experience of the auditory phenomena which are deemed most relevant to the designer. The map should be followed precisely, and participants should walk slowly and quietly in single file, giving each

individual enough distance from the next to avoid potential distractions. There should be pre-established pauses, at regular intervals. During these stops, the soundwalk participants should observe signals, soundmarks and keynotes. Sound recordings can be made using portable audio devices, although this will cause less disruption to listening if handled by a participant tasked solely with making the recordings.

AN ANTHROPOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION

Notes should be taken during pauses, much in the same way anthropologists take field notes during ethnographic research. Each participant can record short observations in a pocket notebook. Once the soundwalk route has been completed, the guide should promote a discussion of the participants' perceptions and interpretations. For example, which sounds were liked the most, and why? Which were most disliked? Participant comments must be recorded by the designers for subsequent analysis.

THICK ANALYSIS OF THE SOUNDSCAPE

Soundscape studies uses a variety of different descriptive and explanatory research methods, from soundmaps to descriptive research. Similarly, in interpretive anthropology, the thick description technique aims to provide a comprehensive, contextual account of shared meaning within a specific society (GEERTZ, 1973). Seeing that the native worldview is a significant component to a study and design of soundscapes, an examination of the methodology of interpretative anthropology is presented here.

The thick description is the product of the researcher's interpretation of signs in culture. "Analysis [...] is sorting out the structures of signification [...] and determining their social ground and import" (Ibid, p. 9). These signs are represented in soundscapes in the semiotic dimension of sound.

Proposing the use of a thick analysis of sound is not new (SMITH, 2004), but in the context of this article, it is aimed at attracting attention to human interpretation, and away from a description of the formal acoustic nature of sound itself. Regarding this ethnographic approach, Schafer mentions the importance of understanding "how different groups

of people react differently to sounds" (SCHAFFER, 1977, p. 148) and points to the symbolic nature of sound in stirring "emotions or thoughts" (Ibid., p. 168).

Furthermore, Patton states three important objectives for an interpretive explanation of phenomena: "Confirm what we know that is supported by data, disabuse us from misconceptions, and illuminate important things that we didn't know but should know" (PATTON, 2002, p. 480).

"Interpretation, by definition, goes beyond the descriptive data. Interpretation means attaching significance to what was found, making sense of findings, offering explanation, drawing conclusions, extrapolating lessons, making inferences, considering meanings, and otherwise imposing order on an unruly but certainly patterned world" (Ibid.).

Furthermore, as in the exploratory phase of a territorial sound study, the use of maps can offer valuable contributions. Several Internet-based examples are available which seek to map territory through sound -- these soundmaps contribute to an auditory perspective of social reality. For example, Montréal Sound Map (Figure 1) uses a Google Maps overlay to embed soundscape recordings into the visual interface. By geographically locating the origin of a sound recording, soundmaps offer a faithful representation of the territorial phenomena they ultimately seek to describe.

Figure 1: Montréal Sound Map, (Source: Max Stein and Julian Stein, <http://www.montrealsoundmap.com/?lang=en>, accessed 04/2011)

CONCLUSION

This article has been an effort to discuss the importance of soundscapes as parts of social experience, as well as to present soundscape theory as a means to address how designers can influence that social experience.

The field of sound studies has significant potential when integrated into design, as it not only addresses territorial sound, but the broad role of sound in culture (Pinch & Bijsterveld, 2004). Further development of the study of urban soundscapes could be in the contextualization of their role in a variety of specific design projects.

A view of a responsible practice of sound design has also been expounded here. As John Cage demonstrates in his piece, 4'33", sound is constantly present, even during periods where the receiver interprets silence. Everest illustrates how we are unable to truly experience silence in his description of a listening activity in an anechoic chamber, where, in the absence of environmental sound, the sound of the body comes to the forefront of hearing: it is the "loud pounding" of the heart as well as the "blood coursing through the vessels" (EVEREST, 2001, p. 42).

Furthermore, territorial sound is heard regardless of listening -- we cannot avoid this stimulus through physical effort, unless we use some device as an obstacle (earplugs or walls, for example). And some obstacles are inadequate in blocking sound propagation -- low frequency sound can easily pass through some walls (EVEREST, 2001). If the researcher takes into account the potentially harmful health effects of intense and continuous sound, then, perhaps, that researcher will endeavor for a balanced and careful treatment of territorial sound elements.

The design of soundscapes can be a significant practice within design. It is relevant in the context of shopping centers, urban parks and residential neighborhoods. It can contribute to coherent marketing communications from companies. However, the challenges of sound design are more likely to be associated to responsibly influencing the subject's cultural interpretations, and to its instrumental role in offering a refuge from an ever growing barrage of multisensory stimuli in society.

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